

Microdetermination of Residues of Lasso (2-chloro-2', 6'-diethyl-N-methoxymethyl acetanilide)

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Microdetermination of Lasso (2-chloro-2',6'-diethyl-N-methoxymethyl acetanilide) and its degradation products is done by combustion of few μ l of the solution in a Schoniger flask in excess of oxygen, absorbing the products in the mixture containing 0.1 N NaOH and 3% H_2O_2 and then titrating potentiometrically with $10^{-4}N$ $AgNO_3$. The degradation products of Lasso are then separated, identified by TLC, eluted and then determined similarly. The method has been applied to determine Lasso and its degradation products, extracted from the soil down to 1 ppm.

LASSO is a selective, pre-emergence herbicide. Its common name is Alachlor and structural formula is :

It is chemically 2-chloro-2', 6' diethyl-N(methoxymethyl)acetanilide. Its solubility in water is 148 ppm but it is freely soluble in organic solvents. It is used for controlling many grasses and broad leaf weeds in groundnut, soybean, cotton, sugarcane, potatoes etc.

Analytical methods except the one based on gas liquid chromatograph are not available for the determination of Lasso and it was, therefore, desirable to work out a method for the estimation of its residues and the degradation products.

Material :

1. Schoniger flask (1 lit)
2. Thin layer chromatographic apparatus suitable for the preparation of thin-layer plates, 20 × 20 cm, with a layer thickness of 250 microns.
3. Systronic pH meter.
4. Soil (Palampur) pH 5.7 E.C. 0.30. Organic matter % 1.10, and Texture Loam.
5. Lasso (91.7%) supplied by Monsanto Chemical Company.

Reagents :

- All reagents should be of analytical grade.
1. Sodium hydroxide (0.1N)

2. Hydrogen peroxide (3%)
3. Silica gel G—for thin layer chromatography.

Potentiometric determination :

The method is based on the combination of the material in excess of oxygen gas in the Schoniger¹ flask and absorbing the products of combustion in a mixture of H_2O_2 and NaOH. The chloride ion in the extract is determined by potentiometric titration with 0.0001 N $AgNO_3$.

Procedure :

An accurately measured volume (few μ l) of the solution of Lasso in benzene, of known concentration (μ g) was applied on an ashless filter paper carrier and mounted on a platinum holder. Three ml of 3% H_2O_2 , 5 ml of 0.1 N NaOH and 2 ml of deionised water were taken in the Schoniger flask. The absorbing solution was then flushed with oxygen for 30 s.c.c. The wick of the filter paper was ignited and the stopper replaced quickly. The flask was tilted very gently and slowly to seal the joint till the combustion was complete. The flask was then allowed to stand for 30 min with occasional shaking. The contents were then transferred to a beaker giving 3-4 washings to the flask with deionised water. This solution was then titrated potentiometrically with 0.0001 N $AgNO_3$ using the electrode system :

The e.m.f. was plotted against the volume of silver nitrate solution. From the curve the volume V of $AgNO_3$ used for titration was determined.

The amount of Lasso (μ g) = $26.95 \times V$.

The minimum amount of Lasso which can be determined by this method is found to be 1 ppm. However, the volume to be taken for combustion should contain at least 10 μ g of Lasso.

When Lasso is applied to the soil, it is adsorbed as well as degraded. The presence of Lasso and its

degradation products in the soil were determined by thin layer chromatography after extraction with benzene and the necessary clean up. A known concentration of Lasso say C_1 , was applied to one gram of Palampur soil and then the solution was separated from the solid after 2 days by centrifuging. The extract in benzene was concentrated to a small volume in vacuum. A few microlitres were taken for potentiometric determination. This gave the total amount of chlorine in Lasso and its degradation products.

Procedure for TLC :

The constituents of the extract were separated by TLC using the solvent system benzene : water : methanol in the ratio 2 : 1 : 1. The mixture was shaken well and the upper layer was used as the solvent.

Glass plates of 20 × 20 cm size were coated uniformly with a slurry of silica gel G and then activated at 110° for 45 min. A few microlitres of the concentrated extract was applied to the chromatoplate (250 u) and developed with the solvent for 45 min. The chromatoplate was allowed to dry and then it was placed in an iodine chamber. After a few minutes the plate was removed and without delay the outlines of the developed spots were marked. Three spots were obtained.

A standard solution (0.1 ml) of Lasso containing 360 µg/ml was also spotted along with the solution of Lasso residue and two spots were obtained from the standard solution. No interference of any other compound was found on the TLC plate and the spots obtained were very clear. The R_f values of these spots were found to be identical with those of two lower spots of solutions of Lasso residue. Out of these two spots the lower one was that of Lasso and the upper one was that of an additive in the product. The intensity of the upper spot was much less than that of lower spot. Thus out of three spots obtained with solution of the residue, the upper most spot was that of degradation product of Lasso which was identified to be 2-chloro-2', 6'-diethyl acetanilide. This was eluted with benzene and thus the amount was determined by the method described.

The area of the lowest spot which was identified to be Lasso was determined. The concentration was calculated from the standard curve previously drawn by plotting the square root of the area against the logarithm of the concentration. The concentration of the herbicide thus obtained was used to calculate the residue present in total volume of the extract.

The R_f values of Lasso and other products are given below.

TABLE 1. THE R_f VALUES OF DIFFERENT CONSTITUENTS

Compound	R_f value
Lasso	0.44
Additive in Lasso	0.64
Degradation product of Lasso	0.94

The results of potentiometric determination are given in Table 2 and show a good agreement between experimentally determined values and the given value.

TABLE 2. POTENTIOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF LASSO (91.7%)

Lasso (µg)	Lasso determined potentiometrically (µg)	% Lasso	% Deviation
72	62.86	87.3	-4.4
144	128.88	89.5	-2.2
216	194.40	90.0	-1.3
288	260.30	90.4	-1.3
360	323.80	89.94	-1.76
432	392.26	90.8	-0.9

On the average, derivation from original value is -2.04%.

In another experiment known quantities of Lasso dissolved in benzene were added to 1 g each of Palampur soil and then incubated for 2 days at 25° with occasional shaking. The solution was separated by centrifugation. Lasso and its degradation product were determined by the method described above. The results are given below in Table 3.

TABLE 3. LASSO AND THE DEGRADATION PRODUCT EXTRACTED FROM PALAMPUR SOIL

Lasso added (µg)	Lasso determined potentiometrically in the extract	Lasso from TLC (µg)	Amount degraded (µg)	% loss
C_1	C_2	C_3		
68.8	40.00	26.67	13.33	41.86
91.70	51.30	33.97	17.33	44.05
366.80	205.00	137.55	67.45	44.11
550.20	316.44	216.00	100.44	42.49
733.60	370.32	236.93	133.39	57.69

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Reference

1. W. SCHONIGER, *Mikrochim. Acta.*, 1956, 896.